

HISTORICAL AND PHILOSOPHICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE IDEA OF NATIONAL INDEPENDENCE OF FINE ARTS

ABSTRACT

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INTRODUCTION

The development of milium spiritualism in the years of justice was imagined without the image of Fine Art. Independent ideological significance is one of the ancient people-it is the content that determines and based on the rich image of the works of art that represent the reached bulmaidi. Because Fine Art is a way of life of being, Historia, Modern Art, has sought tanswirling. I. Karimov worked in detail on this Khazi's "history without umasiz future cargo" (1998). Also towards our dads ancient monuments burned Omar artists historical memories narodimiz high Salahii, KCH-force, founder, glorious long-haired and insatiable of our motherland, dilidiskhuddavsky nobleman. Fine art composer artist izhodi, narodimizning uziga typical turmush lifestyle, lifestyle and life support exponent of etuvchi people

ABSTRACT

Pen drawing methodical methods of fine art composition. Portrait, the significance of the historical and philosophical foundations of the idea of national independence in the depiction of the human figure in practice.

agzaki izhodi sempalari - "Alpomish", "Shashkom" kabi durmonalari, Spitamen, J.Manguberdi, A.Timur kabi Milli ideologiz oziklanadigan manbalaridir. Ideologizing philosophical fundamental National contemplation could give an example of bulgan duneviy bilimlar, zhakhon filosofhasining samonalari belgilaidi. The art of mir and adamning yaratilishi, uning the story of hakidag Diniya and nii Karashlar, poklik, halollik, mardlik and komillik are ideas of both ideology and ideology.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The ideas of our great ancestors about freedom, the secular discoveries of Al-Khorezmi, the moral views of Beruni the doctrine of Fair Society of Farabi, A.The idea of a perfect human being, the views and activities of the jadid enlightenment are considered to be the National idea and

the ideology of independence. The philosophical basis of the ideology of national independence also rests on the legacy of the ancient eastern, Greek, Roman and other schools of philosophy. In particular, the views of such philosophers as Socrates, Plato, Aristotle are of great importance for substantiating and enriching the ideology of national independence. Confucius's philosophical convictions, Plato's doctrine of the "world of ideas and the world of ideas", Hegel's dialectics, ideas promoted by humanistic modern philosophical currents also form the Universal foundations of the ideology of national independence. Thanks to the personality of Timur, the origin of Uzbeks and what historical, natural laws and factors of the Uzbek people, we can imagine through the works of architectural monuments of the historical great similar battlefields of Uzbek Fine Arts. Types of fine arts painting, graphics, haikaltoroshlik yunalishlari a national idea in the work of many famous artists, Historical Philosophical contemporary compositions famous artists who created in the technology of machine painting: Malik Nabiev is named after the historical great Simons A. Timur portrait compositions, Monumental painting Alisher Alikulov great Mercury compositions A. Timur's compositions, khaykaltorash Ilkhom Jabarov A. Timur portrait human komati monumental compositions are installed on the squares of many regions. Workshop painting, architectural art, artist, art teacher fine art independent scientific

¹ .Б.Ф. жабборов Содержание формирования эстетических представлений у младших школьников в семье. ЕВРАЗИЙСКИЙ НАУЧНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ №2 февраль 2018, Россия. Санкт-Петербург

researcher, researcher R Dzhaliyeva A. Timur's composition is characteristic of various battles, battlefields batal painting and painting Uzi. His work the years of independence of Uzbekistan and world-renowned pottery, architectural loychs painting works are unique. His illustrated works, scientific articles are active participants in numerous Republican regional foreign competitions.

The wide development of folk handicrafts, applied decorative arts, architecture and especially fine arts plays an important role in the historical and cultural civilization of the people of the world. For example, in the past, the sculptural type of fine arts as an effective source of creativity has become an integral part of the artistic culture of many peoples and nations. In particular, the sculpture of Uzbekistan has examples of creativity that echo from distant historical times, which are a rare heritage of our ancient past.²

2009 visual arts weekly personal exhibition "bakhori ilkhomlanib" Tashkent creative Association of the Academy of Arts of Uzbekistan professor a Egamov, art critic N. Abdullaev, magazines artist M. Qabilov, Damir Urazov teachers, art historians were highly appreciated by scientists they are in their opinion: Independence years artists' creativity "qaltasvir" scientific doctoral candidate O'kov manual takdimoti kamissiya yuuqori was appreciated.

² Dilmurod Saymamutovich Pulatov
Formation of Ancient Sculpture on the Territory of Uzbekistan. Email:

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History of the schools of Fine Arts of Uzbekistan and philosophical contemporary directions the opinion of scientists art historians scientific articles scientific journals, conference conferences on the basis of taxlil were published. Scientific brochures, creative catalog, personal exhibitions in 2009 at the personal exhibition " bakhordan ilkhomlab", famous arlari "Samarkand", "mother" "Shakhmaordon", "bakhor in Tashkent" landscapes," architecture yay legend " composition XV captive Turkmenistan facade kurinishi badiy decoration uzinirng ancient legends by the artist hayoti vagiyas, painting mazayka technology³ modern image symbolism, abstract yunalish composition took place in the hearts of the audience. The works were supplemented by the Diploma of the most active painting master. Musavvira's works in painting historicism, philosophy, aesthetics symbolic symbolism reflected images in different genres. The composition" legend and self-portrait " is the image of a dragon who is looking for the world, Mother, woman, God, family, parishioners, flower gnats, humanity, nature, Salvation Mechir, bird of happiness on an apple tree, a mother flying over a blue sky the compote of protecting children like an autumn brunette is reflected in the abstract modern yunalish. In his mind, the great scientist mutafakir described the world as the sweet momila of Good Evil: a person cannot realize himself without realizing his moral duty. Fights against ignorance is a fundamental quality. Tree nature, monsters, people love people,

³ BAKHTIYOR RUZINOV.....Jamiyat va innovatsiyalar
.http://inscience.uz/index.php/socinov/ondex

kindness, humanity. Man should be answered with good for good. The truth of the word is the truth, the truth is the truth. He gives determination to man, opposes humbleness, the philosopher says that the symbol of Justice "a wise man seeks justice, and paskash says manfaat" Confucius [2.13]. Teacher trainer's day" Flowers of my village to you saints", it is appropriate if we compare the material and spiritual world, necessary for the realization of human-specific dreams, for him to live a fulfilling life, to the two wings of a bird flying calmly [1.67]. In this world, the idea of the work and the composition of the works of human beings burn their faces. Museum and children's day "happy childhood", 2016yil" Uzbekistan gulla yashna "Independence Day 2022 personal exhibitions" from The New History of Uzbekistan ilkhomlab " painting and pencil painting composition scientific research new history pages of musavvira drawing a picture from nature in front of the workshop easel, Plener. R Dzhaliyeva personal exhibitions of the charm of colors of the Independence years of Uzbekistan do not look like one, each of the works reminds of historical utmish. "Emir Timur, Z.M.Babur, M.The methodology of the composition" Ulugbek", which is described by scientific practical sketches of his imagination and creativity, differs in color style. His work, called the Iron battlefield, was rich in events, and his image, which showed courage on the battlefields, was created by a composite idea. On the square mountains of water fire to cleanse their homeland from the invaders from the hustle and bustle of different nature. Portrait of Amir Timur, a Sahibkiran, a commander of loyalty and dedication to his homeland, is reflected in a military dress it

is carried out. Musavvir described various curinis by beating the work carried out by the portraits of the great figures. The historical davir Amir Temur image is the images that have been mastered and re-materialized by the creator of real Carias. When Musavvir describes historical vagia, it is through the image that he seeks to make her look like herself that davir tries to express his opinion on the nature of his character. Books, magazines, Internet information based on historical sources give the artist the illusion of Amir Timur and other great Simons kunikma tasurot. The composition in the image of the meaning (Battle) of the word Battalion. In the works of ancient fine art in Central Asia, by the XIV century in Samarkand, the walls of the palaces of Amir Timur "garden-Wind", "Garden-Dilkusho", during military campaigns, battles and hunting ceremonies, Timur was depicted by the miniature artist of his time Akhmad - garden - wind with his concubines, Amir, Princes. In the XIV century, the Batal genre is waiting for a development pit in miniatures. The famous painting master of the XIX century is considered In the works of the famous Malik Nabiev, Kamolddin

Bekhzad, the battle and portrait of a person's external and internal policy, his psyche, costumes of the genre of the landscape in nature pass the background task and help the composition to perform more vividly. Protect the motherland, Outlined in general terms. Pictured is the object color-blue, crust or eleven, kechasi, tun Kunduz Kunduz, ularda dil oromining the influence of ohangi, naturning buyuk uygunligi-heart temperature, hoarseness of voice, singshib ketishi yakol photo this is turadi.

Conclusion :Tarihiy and sovremennytasvir release artist izhodida baziyy Urin egallaidi. Buyuk fine art master izhodi K.Behzod miniatura art, dislocated yillari fine art master artist, for example, Kulyab science statyar yeritildi. Portrait man standing essay, nature coursework, being coursework, Tarikh Buyuk symbol in the images of the analysis of ethics, theoretical guidance. Amir Temur, Z.M.Bobir M.Ulugbek lives a modern life tarihiy vakiyalar illustrator buyuk artist izhodiyy works of science theorist urganildi, amalda illustrator analysis of ethyldi.Eslar spirituality kamolatida image sana aslar tarihi and philosopher

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